

ASSESSMENT OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS FINANCING ACTIVITIES AMONG SMALL & MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN PLATEAU STATE.

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Abstract

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are critical to the development of any economy as they possess great potentials for development of indigenous entrepreneurship, employment output diversification, and so on. However, in developing countries, particularly Nigeria, SMEs find it difficult to obtain finance thus lack access to capital and money markets. Despite efforts by financial institutions and public sector bodies to close funding gaps, SMEs continue to experience difficulties in obtaining capital. This study examined the benefits that SMEs in Plateau State derive from Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) financing. Using a quantitative method via survey, 280 questionnaires were distributed to different owners of SMEs in Jos North, Plateau State. Data analysis was carried out via descriptive statistics and Chi-Square. The study findings indicate that SMEs obtain finance from Deposit Money Banks, and the obtained loan aided the growth and development of SMEs significantly. This study concludes that SMEs obtain finance from Deposit Money Banks, and the obtained loan has significant impact on the growth and development of SMEs hence government policies should aim to reduce cumbersome procedure, collateral requirement and timely sanctioning of loan defaulters. The study recommends that government should compel DMBs to focus more on financing SMEs at startup, as well as relax the interest rates.

Keywords: *Deposit Money Banks, Finance, Growth, SMEs*

Introduction

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are critical to the development of any economy as they possess great potentials for employment generation, improvement of local technology, output diversification, development of indigenous entrepreneurship and forward integration with large-scale industries. In Nigeria, there has been gross underperformance of the SMEs sub-sector and this has undermined its contribution to economic growth and development. The key issues affecting SMEs in the country can be grouped into four namely: unfriendly business environment, poor funding, low managerial skills and lack of access to modern technology (Onwumere, 2000).

International Finance Corporation (IFC) shows that approximately 96% of Nigerian businesses are SMEs (Oyelarín-Oyeyinka, 2010). SMEs represent about 90% of the manufacturing/industrial

sector in terms of the number of enterprises in Nigeria. However, although SMEs constitute more than 90% of Nigerian businesses, their contribution to GDP is only about 1%. It has been well established that Fatai (2011) agreed on the point that SME's definition differs from country to country while Oyelarin-Oyeyinka (2010) stated that SMEs are distributed by clusters within regions. Fatai (2011) stated that as a result of the definitional differences of SMEs across countries and the absence of a universal definition, the European Union in 2003 adopted a universally accepted definition of Small and Medium-scale Enterprises and micro business as companies with less than 250 employees, revenues must not exceed 50million euro (turnover) or 43million euro. Oyelarin-Oyeyinka (2010) said in Nigeria SMEs are distributed by clusters within regions, for example, Aba leather and the fashion SMEs cluster, Nnewi automobile SMEs cluster, Lagos Otigba ICT SMEs cluster, Abeokuta and Oshogbo tie and dye SMEs cluster, Kano leather SMEs cluster, and so on.

DMBs are sometimes called commercial banks these are Banks that have specific functions spelled out in the Banking Act they are licensed by the CBN only. Their functions include financial intermediation that is mobilizing deposits from surplus areas and lending it to needy areas of the economy. SMEs are a very needy area for finances and therefore DMBs are their best sources of finance, other sources of finances are available to SMEs but they tend to be more expensive, difficult and even the money in other sources is not as much as the commercial banks. SMEs have four main sources of funding: personal savings, partnership, formal sources, and informal sources. Commercial banks remain the biggest source of funds for SMEs, but some SMEs have refused to borrow due to the perceived risks and uncertainties. In developing countries, SMEs find it difficult to obtain finance. Africa in particular, SMEs lack access to capital and money markets. Despite efforts by financial institutions and public sector bodies to close funding gaps, SMEs continue to experience difficulties in obtaining capital. This is the situation in Nigeria as well. This study investigates the benefits that SMEs in Plateau State derive from DMB funding.

Research Objectives

The general objective of this study is to investigate the benefits that SMEs in Plateau State derive from DMB funding. Our specific objectives include:

- 1) To examine if SMEs obtain finance from DMBs
- 2) To examine if SMEs that obtain finance from DMBs grow
- 3) To examine the difficulties SMEs face in meeting DMB loan conditions

Research Questions

This study asks the following research questions:

- 1) Do SMEs obtain finance from DMBs?
- 2) Do the loan beneficiaries grow?
- 3) What are the difficulties SMEs face when trying to access finance from DMBs?

Research Hypothesis

The following hypotheses are formulated for the study:

- Ho₁: SMEs do not obtain finance from DMBs
- Ho₂: SMEs who obtain finance from DMBs do not grow
- Ho₃: SMEs do not face difficulties in meeting DMBs loan conditions

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

The exact definition of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) depend from country to country as well as which economic scheme is involved. In Nigeria, the definition of SMEs is taken from the meeting of the Nigeria Council of Industry held in July 2001 in Makurdi, Benue State (Obistayo, 2001). Adigwe (2012) defined SME as any industry with a labor size of 11-100 workers or a total cost of not more than N50 million, including working capital and excluding the cost of land. Small and Medium Size Enterprises (SMEs) as defined by the National Council of Industries (2009) refers to business enterprises whose total costs excluding land is not more than two hundred million naira (₦200,000,000) only. However, it has been suggested that the SMEs sub-sector may comprise about 87% of all firms operating in Nigeria, excluding informal-enterprises. Imoughele and Ismaila (2014) defined enterprises as informal businesses employing fewer workers including unpaid family labor. Small scale enterprises are those operating in a formal sector with five to twenty employees, and medium enterprises are those employing 21 to 50 employees. The Nigerian concepts of SMEs are somewhat divergent but the Central Bank of Nigeria agrees with the Small and Medium Industries and Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS) in their definition of SME as any enterprise with a maximum asset base less than ₦200 million (equivalent of about \$1.43 million) excluding land and working capital, and with the number of staff employed not less than 10 (otherwise will be a cottage or micro-enterprise) and not more than 300.

Ayeni-Agbaje and Osho (2015) observed that SME has a long history like every other part of the world. Historically, Small and Medium enterprises have their origin in the eastern and Mediterranean, Small and Medium Enterprises, all over the world are divergent arrays of business concerns involved in economic activities sparring from micro and rural enterprises to contemporary industrial organizations that use sophisticated technologies. In Nigeria, there is no generally accepted definition of SMEs but it varies over time from organization to organization. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) (2003) defined SME as an enterprise with a maximum asset base of NGN 200 million, without land and working capital, also the number of employees is not less than 10 and not more than 300. Due to the flexible nature, SMEs are quite able to withstand economically diverse situations. SMEs in Nigeria can be categorized into urban and rural enterprises, but more formally, they can be called organized and unorganized enterprises. The organized enterprises have paid employees with a registered office while the unorganized enterprises rely mostly on apprentices or family members and mostly low rate or no salary paid workers. Rural enterprises are made up of artisans who work in open spaces. Rural enterprises are made up of family groups, women that are engaged in food production from local farm crops and individual artisans (Okonkwo, et. al. 2019; Okonkwo, et. al. (2017). The major activities are leather, local blacksmith, tinsmith, ceramic, clothing and tailoring, timber and winning, bricks and cement, food processing, wood furniture, beverages, bakeries, electronic assembly, agro-processing, chemical-based products, and mechanics.

According to history, SMEs in Nigeria have existed since the country's independence in 1960, probably before independence but since independence, Nigeria has had series of seminars, studies, and workshops, each of which appraises the excellence, importance and need to facilitate the establishment and sustainability of SMEs. Besides the Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) initiation in 1986, the state did not appreciate the structural adjustment program's active involvement in industrialization by a

process of commercialization and privatization. According to Chinedu et al. (2019), the objective of SMEs in Nigeria is to produce and distribute goods and services to their customers at a reasonable price and reasonable profit, and its importance include creation of employment, skill acquisition, increase standard of living, increase government earnings, and accelerate large production.

Deposit Money Banks

Deposit Money Banks are also commercial banks. Imoughele and Ismaila (2014) defined a commercial bank as a financial institution that is authorized by law to receive money from businesses and individuals and lend money to them. Commercial banks also allow for a variety of deposit accounts, such as checking, savings, and time deposit. Commercial banks are open to the public and serve individuals, institutions, and businesses. These banks are regulated by federal and state laws depending on services provided. DMBs are monitored through the Federal Reserve System.

The principal function of commercial banks according to Ayeni-Agbaje and Osho (2015) include acceptance of deposits on fixed, current and savings account, advancing loans by ways of loans, overdraft and discounting bills of exchange, acting as an agent to their customers by buying and selling of shares and stocks on behalf of their customers, issuing travelers cheques and draft etc. and as trustees, executors and also as referees to firms and individuals and providing facilities for safekeeping of wills and other documents as well as jewelries. Lending is a major function that commercial banks perform. Commercial banks in playing their intermediation role do give their deposits mobilized out to the deficit economic unit as a loan, which may be on a short, medium or long-term basis. Since there are many studies in respect of bank's lending behavior, it is therefore imperative to highlight and consider some factors that economists and professionals alike have proposed as virtually significant in explaining the determinant of commercial banks' lending behaviour (Olokoyo, 2012; Ugwa, et. al. 2019). Lending is indubitably the heart of the banking business. For that reason, its administration requires considerable skill and dexterousness on the part of the bank management. Commercial banking in Nigeria witnessed an era of impressive profitability, characterized by high competition, huge deposits, and varied investment opportunities; to make quick profits the commercial banks relied essentially on self-liquidating loans and diversified their portfolio into less risky investments with a safe margin. The current trend in the Nigerian banking and finance sector, suggests that the days of cheap profits are now over and only banks with well-conceptualized lending and credit administration policies and procedures can survive the emerging competition (Olokoyo, 2006).

Bank Financing and SMEs Growth

SMEs are crucial catalysts for economic development (Aruwa, 2015). Banks provide a nation with a function of pooling scattered resources from surplus to deficit units to promote investment innovation, productivity and consequently growth and development. The banking industry in Nigeria dominates the financial system. Berger and Udell (1995) maintain that a well functioning financial system contributes to investment and economic growth. Every enterprise at its onset, before standing firm on its feet, needs borrowing. The first place that they need to go and borrow at those times is the banks. According to elementary corporate finance theory, an investment project should be undertaken whenever its net present value is positive. This assumes that the capital expenditure is not exhaustive. Firms do any volume of investment, and so where the firms do not have sufficient capital to embark on any level of investment, there is a need for capital borrowing. This shows that even if an enterprise

is strong and firmly rooted, it still does not stop borrowing, because it can embark on a very large-scale investment more than it currently does if it can get the required capital. In an economy where the interest rate is high, Small and Medium Enterprises find it difficult to borrow and repay when in fact they constitute the real sector of the economy.

When funding becomes a major problem for such enterprises, nothing else works. This is because of other problems, which emerge later in, an enterprise's lives that are being tackled as natural problems, which come after its funding. This, in turn, hinders the growth and development of the economy. Njoku (2007) argued that to forestall the imminent capital flight from the real sector to the banking sector, Banks should begin to take a second look at the industrial sector in terms of lending operations. He continues that banks should plow back a large proportion of the money available to them to the real sector of the economy as long-term loans at rates not exceeding 5%. This he said will encourage industrialists not only to remain in their present businesses but also to achieve their business expansion targets. Small and medium scale enterprises dominate the private sector of the Nigerian economy, but almost all of them are starved of funds (Njoku, 2007; Odoanyanwu, et. al. 2017; Onwuka, et. al. 2017). The persistent lack of finance, for establishment and operation of SMEs occasioned by the inability or unwillingness of the Deposit Money Banks to grant long term credit to operators of the real sector of the economy, led to the establishment of development finance institutions and the introduction of numerous funding programs for the development of SMEs in Nigeria.

In spite of these institutions and funding programs, there continues to be a persistent cry against inadequate finance for the development of the SMEs in the country. CBN (2003) report shows that commercial and merchant bank loans, and advances to SMEs have been decreasing over the years. The statistics show thus: commercial bank's loans to SMEs as a percentage of total credit decreased from 48.8% in 2008 to 22.22% in 2010. The trend increased marginally to 22.9 and 25.5% in 2012 and 2014, respectively. There was a sharp reduction from 25 to 17% in 2015, and the decrease continued till it reached 0.2% in the year 2016. Similarly, merchant bank loans to SMEs as a percentage of total credits reduced from 31.2% in 2009 to 9.0% in 2011 (Akabueze, 2002). The continuous decrease in commercial and merchant bank loans to small-scale enterprises can be attributed to the lack of collateral from the SMEs to secure the loans as well as high lending rates from the banks.

Theoretical Review

Theories are formulated to explain, predict and understand phenomena and, in many cases to challenge and extend existing knowledge within the limits of critical bounding assumptions. The theoretical framework is the structure that can hold or support a theory of a research study. This study adopts the supply leading and credit rationing theories.

The supply leading theory postulates that the existence of financial institutions like deposit money banks and the supply of their financial assets, liabilities and related financial services in advance of demand for them would provide efficient allocation of resources from surplus units to deficit units, thereby leading the other economic sectors in their growth process (Patrick, 1966). This theory performs two functions: first, it transfers resources from traditional sectors to modern sectors; and second, it promotes and stimulates an entrepreneurial response (SMEs) in the modern sectors. Early economist like Schumpeter (1911) strongly supported the view of a finance-led causal relationship between financing of small-medium enterprises and a country economic growth. The supply-leading financial intermediation can be linked to the term innovation finance (Schumpeter,

1911). Hence, one of the most significant effects of the supply-leading approach is that, as entrepreneurs have new access to the supply-leading funds, their expectations increase and new horizons as to possible alternatives are opened, thereby making the entrepreneur think big.

The credit rationing model emanated from the revolutionary work of Stiglitz and Weiss (1981). According to Stiglitz and Weiss (1981) lenders seek to impose quantitative restrictions on the amount of debt the borrower can obtain, so-called equilibrium quantity rationing of credit, because higher interest rates may give a further stimulus to adverse selection and risk-taking. The model assumes the existence of many banks that seek to maximize their profits through their choice of interest and collateral (thereby reducing the probability of default on their loans) and many potential borrowers who seek to maximize their profits through the choice of projects (Okurut et al., 2011). Access to credit is especially restricted for the small and medium enterprises, owing to their inability to provide collateral. Collateral both reduces default risk (for incentive reasons) and lender exposure in the event of default (Ghosh et al., 2000). However, banks exercise caution in their lending behavior and are risk-averse in an environment of uncertainty.

Empirical Review

Kwaning et al. (2015) examined the difficulties SMEs face in accessing a loan, difficulties financial institutions face in lending to SMEs and the impact of the loan on the profitability of SMEs. Questionnaires were administered to SMEs and Credit officers in the selected banks were interviewed. The following major findings came to the fore; interest rate on loan to the SMEs is extremely high, repayment periods on loans to SMEs are too short making it very difficult to embark on any developmental or expansion projects, most SMEs, do not understand terms and conditions, and also oblivious of the interpretation of the percentage charged on the loans. The study also found out that small business owners normally give false information when accessing loans from financial institutions. The study suggested that the government should institute some form of tax incentives to financial institutions involved in SME lending and formulate regulatory laws to help loan recovery. Kehinde and Ashamu (2014) empirically found that 70% of SMEs in Nigeria were operationally active while the collapsible leftover of 30% was in operation to the truncated measurements which were susceptible to seize in operations in the nearest imminent. Adofu et al. (2010) assessed the influence and effectiveness of commercial banks in improving commercial growth in Nigeria and found that credit facilities' issued in agriculture increased the GDP of the country. The study adopted the ordinary least square method. The variable used was commercial bank credit loans to agriculture (SMEs). Uzonwanne (2015) proposed that commercial banks in Nigeria lack a sustainable culture of financing SMEs. The study concluded that financial regulators should initiate policies that will address the issue of finance to SMEs to meet up with the required percentage of borrowing to SMEs.

Ifeakachukwu (2013) examined the impact of banks loan to SMEs on manufacturing output in Nigeria for the period spanning 1992 to 2010. Employing the error correction modeling technique, the study deduced that bank loans to the SME sector had a significant impact on manufacturing output both in the long and short run. Ishmael et al. (2012) examined the impact of post-bank consolidation on the performance of SMEs in Nigeria, with special reference to Lagos State. A sample size of 50 was drawn from the supra-population of the study within the Ikeja Local Government in Lagos State. Applying mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation in its data analysis, the study revealed that SMEs do not have better access to finance through banks, due to neo-reorganization in banks as a

result of post-bank consolidation and SMEs do not have an absolute rapport with the financial institutions due to their financial background in Nigeria. Researchers have found more ways through which SMEs can generate funds for their businesses and they all came up with various theories to support their findings. But the researchers failed to realize that SME continues to experience difficulties in obtaining capital also we are not sure if all the financing options put in place by DMBs help SMEs to grow as expected. Therefore this research will investigate SME's growth using profit and sales turnover as measures and difficulties SMEs encounter when requesting for loan from DMBs.

Methodology

This research adopted a descriptive cross-sectional method to accurately and systematically describe the effect of DMBs financing on SME's growth in Plateau State. This approach adopted an in-depth exploration of data on the nature of the problem. The cross-sectional method collects data from the respondents at a time. According to Nigeria Directory/Plateau State/Jos North LGA, the number of SMEs in Jos North Local Government of Plateau State for the study is 1,560. This population includes provision stores, tailoring, hair dressers, carpenters, shoe making, etc. The sample size was ascertained using the Yamane Formula (Yamane, 1973). According to Yamane (1967): $n = N / 1 + N(e)^2$ where: n = Sample Size, N = Population Size, e = Error of Sampling, $N = 1,560$, $e = 5\%$ (0.05). Therefore: $n = 1,560 / 1 + 1,560(0.05)^2$ thus $n = 399$. Therefore, the sample size is 399 respondents.

The primary data generated for this research was through the use of questionnaire from which the hypotheses were tested. The questionnaire was structured to align with the research objectives, the research questions, and the research hypotheses using close-ended questions. The questionnaires were administered to randomly selected members of SMEs in Plateau State. Chi-Square was used to analyze the data gathered. The formula for the Chi-square is: $X^2 = \sum (fo - fe) / fe$; where X^2 = Chi-square, fo = Observed Actual frequency, fe = Expected frequency, \sum = summation.

Analysis/Findings

The researcher distributed 399 questionnaires to the respondents, 280 were retrieved and used. The following technique of frequency and percentage was applied in order to obtain the percentage on the table below. Thus, $F \times 100 / N$, where F = frequency of a particular response, N = total units, % = percentage

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Responses

S/N	Characteristics	Respondents Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Male	168	60%
		Female	112	40%
		Total	280	100%
2	Age	Below 45	84	30%
		Above 45	196	70%
		Total	280	100%
3	Educational Qualification	Less than 1 st degree	98	35%
		1 st degree/Equivalent	112	40%
		Above 1 st degree	70	25%
		Total	280	100%
4	Business Type	Sole	168	60%
		Proprietorship/Family	84	30%

		Partnership Limited Liability Total	24 280	10% 100%
5	Business Age	Below 5 years 5-10 years 10 years Total	84 154 42 280	30% 55% 15% 100%
6	Do you prepare audited financial account?	Yes No Total	70 210 280	25% 75% 100%
7	Have you ever applied for a loan?	Yes No Total	250 30 280	89% 11% 100%
8	How much did you apply for?	Below 100,000 200,000 – 500,000 1,000,000 – above Total	50 152 78 280	17.9% 54.2% 27.9% 100%
9	What were the loan conditions?	Certificate of registration Business assets Business Financial Statements Business Plan Total	55 95 80 50 280	19.6 33.9 28.6 17.9 100%
10	Was the request approved?	Yes No Total	117 163 280	41.8% 58.2% 100%
11	If not approved, what were the reasons for rejection?	Inadequate business assets Lack of business certification Total	135 145 280	48.2% 51.8% 100%
12	Did you utilize the loan for what it was provided?	Yes No Total	138 142 280	49.3% 50.7% 100%
13	Did you grow from the loan?	Yes No Total	200 80 280	71.4% 28.6% 100%
14	Did you face Any difficulty accessing the loan?	Yes No Total	150 130 280	53.6% 46.4% 100%
15	If yes, describe the difficulty in assessing loan?	Identification of deserving borrower Ultimately sanctioning loan Cumbersome problem Collateral requirement Total	80 50 50 100 280	28.5% 17.9% 17.9% 35.7% 100%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 1 indicates that 168 of the respondents which represent 60% of the respondents are male while 40% are female. This implies that majority of the respondents are male, 30% of the respondents are below 45 years while 70% of the respondents are above 45 years, 25% of the respondents have less than 1st Degree, 40% of the respondents have 1st Degree holders and 35% of the respondents have above 1st Degree holders which implies that 1st Degree/Equivalent are the majority of the respondents, 168 respondents representing 60% are Sole proprietorship/Family, 84 respondents representing 30% are partnership and 28 respondents representing 10% are limited liability, 84 respondents representing

30% are below 5 years in business, 154 respondents representing 55% are 5-10 years and 42 respondents representing 15% are 10 years and above in the business, 70 respondents representing 25% prepare audited financial account while 280 respondents representing 75% do not prepare audited financial account, 250 respondents representing 89% asserted that they have applied for a loan while 30 respondents representing 11% had a contrary opinion, 50 respondents representing 17.9% applied for loan below 100,000, 152 respondents representing 54.2 applied for 200,000 – 500,000 and 78 respondents representing 27.9% applied for 1,000,000 and above, 55 respondents representing 19.6 assert that their loan condition was certificate of registration, 95 respondents constituting 33.9% said business assets, 80 respondents constituting 28.6% said business financial statements and 50 respondents representing 17.9% said their loan condition was business plan, 117 respondents which constitute 41.8% said yes while 163 respondents constituting 58.2% said no. This revealed that majority of the SMEs who applied for loan did not meets the loan conditions and only 41.8% of the were given loan, 135 respondents which constitutes 48.2% said inadequate business assets makes their loan request to be rejected while 145 respondents representing 51.8 said lack of certificate of incorporation makes their loan request to be rejected. This implies that lack of business assets and certificate of incorporation makes the loan request of SMEs to be rejected. Also the table shows that 138 respondents representing 49.3% said they have utilized the loan for which it was provided for while 142 respondents representing 50.7% said no, 136 respondents constituting 48.5% of the SMEs asserts that the loan has improve their business by increasing their profit level while the remaining 144 respondents representing 51.5% said the loan has helped them to acquire more business assets, 200 respondents which constituted 71.4% of the SMEs are of the opinion that they have grown from the loan while 80 respondents constituting 28.6% has a contrary opinion, 150 respondents representing 53.6% said yes while 130 respondents representing 46.4% said no. this implies that most of the SMEs face difficulty in accessing the loan, 80 respondents representing 28.5% said identification of deserving borrowers is the difficulty they faced in accessing loan, 50 respondents representing 17.9% said untimely sanctioning of loan, 50 respondents representing 17.9% said cumbersome procedure and 100 respondents representing 35.7% said collateral requirement makes it difficult for them to access loan.

Test of Hypothesis One: SMEs do not obtain finance from DMBs

Table 2: Contingency Table for Testing Hypothesis One

Question	Yes	No	Total
Have you ever applied for loan?	250	30	280
Was the request approved?	117	163	280
Total	367	193	560

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 3: Chi-square(χ^2) Table testing Hypothesis one

Fo	Fe	Fo – fe	(fo – fe) ²	(fo – fe) ² / Fe
250	427.2	-177.2	31399.8	522.4
117	427.2	-310.2	96224	-0.814
30	98.6	-68.6	-4705	-156
163	98.6	64.4	4147.3	25.4
				X ² =390.986

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Considering the fact that the calculated X^2 (390.986) is less than the table value of X^2 (411.67). Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) which states that “SMEs do not obtain finance from DMBs”.

Test of Hypothesis Two: SMEs who obtain finance from DMBs do not grow

Table 4: Contingency Table for Testing Hypothesis Two

Question	Yes	No	Total
Did you utilize the loan for what it was provided	138	142	280
Did you grow from the loan	200	80	280
Total	338	222	560

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 5: Chi-square(x^2) Table Testing Hypothesis Two

Fo	Fe	Fo – fe	(fo – fe) ²	(fo – fe) ² / Fe
138	463.9	-325.9	-106210	-769.6
200	463.9	-263.9	-69643	150.1
142	706.3	-1454.3	-211498	-299.5
80	706.3	-626.3	392251.7	555.3
				$X^2 =$ 363.8

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Considering the fact that the calculated X^2 (363) is less than the table value of X^2 . Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) which states that “SMEs who obtain finance from DMBs, do not improve.”

Test of Hypothesis Three: SMEs do not face difficulties in meeting DMBs loan conditions

Table 6: Contingency Table for Testing Hypothesis Three

Question	Yes	No	Total
Did you face any difficulty accessing the loan	150	130	280
Total	150	130	280

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 7: Chi-square(x^2) Table Testing Hypothesis Three

Fo	Fe	Fo – fe	(fo – fe) ²	(fo – fe) ² / Fe
150	522	-372	138384	-264.1
130	603	-472	222784	-369.4
				$X^2 =$ 633.5

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Considering the fact that the calculated X^2 (-633.5) is less than the table value of X^2 . Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) which states that “SMEs do not face difficulties in meeting DMBs loan conditions”.

Discussions/Implications

In hypothesis one, the null hypothesis which states that SMEs do not obtain finance from Deposit Money Banks is rejected, the alternative hypothesis is to be accepted. This is seen from table one where 250 respondents representing 89% of the SMEs asserted that they have ever applied for a loan. In hypothesis two, the null hypothesis which states that “SMEs who obtain finance from DMBs, do not improve” was rejected as the calculated X^2 was less than the table value of X^2 . It was discovered that 138 respondents representing 49.3% said they utilize the loan for what it was provided for while 142 respondents representing 50.7% they did not utilize the loan for what it was been provided for and 136 respondents constituting 48.5% said their profit has improved while the remaining respondents representing 51.5% said their business has acquired more assets. In hypothesis three, the null hypothesis also rejected as responses indicates that 150 respondents representing 53.6% said they faced difficulty in accessing loan. The implication of our findings is that SMEs and SMEs financing is critical to the growth of SMEs, the local and national economy.

Conclusions/Recommendations

Findings from the study revealed that most SMEs that applied for ₦200,000 to ₦500,000 loan request was approved for those who met the loan requirement. Most of the SMEs were asked to provide collateral, some of the collateral asked are: business certificate of registration, business financial statements and others, the loan in which the SMEs requested for was well utilized, despite all these some SMEs still find it difficult in accessing loan due to identification of deserving borrowers, untimely sanctioning of loan, cumbersome procedure and collateral requirement. Small and Medium Scale Enterprises obtain finance from Deposit Money Banks and this loan obtained from Deposit Money Banks has significant impact on the growth and development of SMEs. The researcher also concludes that identification of deserving borrowers, untimely sanctioning of loan, cumbersome procedure and collateral requirement are the difficulties SMEs face in meeting Deposit Money Banks loan conditions.

Based on the result of findings, the researcher hereby gives the following recommendations: since Small and Medium Scale Enterprise obtain finance from Deposit Money Banks, it is recommended that government should compel DMBs to concentrate more on financing SMEs. The difficulty of identification of deserving borrowers, untimely sanctioning of loan, cumbersome procedure and collateral requirement before granting loan should be made flexible as most of the SMEs are startups; government should relax the interest rate especially to those who are into SMEs in order to enhance their business performance thereby reducing the crime rates and improve the standard of living, demanding unattainable security from intending or existing business owners should be reviewed by the law of the land because these are the categories of people adding immediate value to the country economy; and finally, potential business owners should as a matter of necessity learn how to prepare business feasibility study as this will act as a guide that makes the owners of business to remain focused. Time constraint and insufficient funds tends to impede the efficiency of the researcher in sourcing for the relevant materials and in the process of data collection. Future studies may focus on investigating the mediating or moderating variables in the relationship between DMB financing and growth of SMEs. Furthermore, this study can be replicated in a different environment to ascertain environmental factors that could play a positive or negative role in financing.

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